

MULTI-TEMPORAL SAR IMAGE CHANGE DETECTION USING NSCT AND K-MEANS CLUSTERING

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we introduce a change detection technique for synthetic aperture radar (SAR) images based on image fusion and K-means clustering algorithm. The image fusion technique is introduced to generate a difference image using complementary information from a mean-ratio image and a log-ratio image. NSCT (Non-subsampled contourlet transform) based fusion involves an averaging operator and maximum gradient coefficient selection to fuse low-frequency and high-frequency bands to restrain the background information and enhance the information of changed regions in the fused difference image. K-means clustering algorithm is the proposed algorithm for classifying changed and unchanged regions from the fused image with performance analysis.

Keywords: Change detection, Non-Sub-sampled Contourlet Transform (NSCT), K-means clustering algorithm, synthetic aperture radar (SAR) images.

INTRODUCTION

The detection of changes occurring on the earth's surface through the use of multitemporal remote sensing images is one of the most important applications of remote sensing technology. This depends on the fact that, the knowledge of the dynamics of either natural resources or man-made structures is a valuable source of information in decision making. In this context, satellite and airborne remote sensing sensors have proved particularly useful in addressing change-detection applications related to environmental monitoring, agricultural surveys, urban studies, and forest monitoring. Usually, change detection involves the analysis of two co-registered remote sensing images acquired over the same geographical area at different times. Such an analysis is called unsupervised when it aims at discriminating between two opposite classes (which represent changed and unchanged areas) without any prior knowledge about the scene (i.e., no ground truth is available for modeling the classes). In the analysis of multitemporal remote sensing data acquired by (optical) multispectral sensors, various automatic and unsupervised change-detection methods have been developed and described in the literature. Most are based on the so-called difference image (DI). The most popular way of generating the DI is by change vector analysis. This technique exploits a simple vector subtraction operator for the pixel-by-pixel comparison of the two multispectral images under analysis. Synthetic aperture radars have been less exploited than optical sensors in the context of change detection. This is due to the fact that SAR images suffer from the presence of speckle noise that makes it difficult to analyze such imagery, and in particular to perform unsupervised discrimination between changed and unchanged classes. Despite the presence of speckle noise, the use of SAR sensors in change detection is potentially attractive from the operational viewpoint. These active microwave sensors present the advantage that (unlike optical ones) they are independent of atmospheric and sunlight conditions.

Multi temporal image change detection in the state of remotely sensed natural surfaces by observing them at different times is one of the most important applications of Earth orbiting satellite sensors because they can provide multi date digital imagery with consistent image quality, at short intervals, on a global scale, and during complete seasonal cycles. A lot of experience has already been accumulated in exploring change detection techniques for visible and near infrared data collected by Landsat. In the case of space borne synthetic aperture radar (SAR) imagery, change detection techniques have been developed for the

temporal tracking of multiyear sea-ice floes using Seasat SAR observations, and rainfall events have been detected based on spatial radiometric variations in multirate Seasat SAR imagery. Seasat SAR, however, did not provide calibrated radar measurements, and multirate observations were produced in limited quantity due to the short duration of the mission.

Change detection techniques for space borne SAR data have not yet been fully explored. Change detection techniques for SAR data can be divided into several categories, each corresponding to different image quality requirements. In a first category, changes are detected based on the temporal tracking of objects or stable image features of recognizable geometrical shape. Absolute calibration of the data is not required, but the data must be rectified from geometric distortions due to differences in imaging geometry or SAR processing parameters, and the accurate spatial registration of the multirate data is essential. Combining information acquired from multiple sensors has become very popular in many signal and image processing applications. In the case of earth observation applications, there are two reasons for it. The first one is that the fusion of the data produced by different types of sensors provides complementary information which overcomes the limitations of a specific kind of sensor. The other reason is that, often, in operational applications, the user does not have the possibility to choose the data to work with and has to use the available archive images or the first acquisition available after an event of interest. This is particularly true for monitoring applications where image registration and change detection approaches have to be implemented on different types of data. Both image registration and change detection techniques consist of comparing two images: the reference and the secondary image, acquired over the same landscape scene at two different dates.

Usually, the reference image is obtained from an archive and the acquisition of the secondary image is scheduled after an abrupt change, like a natural disaster. In the case of the change detection, the goal is to produce an indicator of change for each pixel of the region of interest. This indicator of change is the result of applying locally a similarity measure to the two images. This similarity measure is usually chosen as the correlation coefficient or other statistical feature in order to deal with noisy data. The estimation of the similarity measure is performed locally for each pixel position.

PROPOSED METHOD

A. Difference Image Creation

The first step of this process is to generate difference images to enhance details about changes between source images. Here rationing is performed to obtain difference images in logarithmic and mean scale. It is highly robust to speckle noise. Logarithmic scale based difference part is generated to identify the changed and unchanged region and it weakens the high intensity and enhances the low intensity pixels. Due to this weakening, there is a possibility of loss of information from the significant parts. So along with this, mean ratio operator and fusion approaches are used to reduce this limitation and produce accurate detection of changes. The ratio difference image is usually expressed in a logarithmic or a mean scale because of the presence of speckle noise. In the past decade, there was a widespread concern over the logarithm of the ratio image since the log-normal model was considered a heuristic parametric probability distribution function for SAR intensity and amplitude distributions. With the log-ratio operator, the multiplicative speckle noise can be transformed into an additive noise component. Furthermore, the range of variation of the ratio image is compressed thereby enhancing the low-intensity pixels. A ratio mean detector (RMD) could also be used, which is robust to speckle noise. This detector assumes that a change in the scene appears as a modification of the local mean value of the image. Both methods have yielded effective results for the change detection in SAR imagery but still have some disadvantages: The logarithmic scale is characterized by enhancing the low-intensity pixels while weakening the pixels in the areas of high intensity; therefore, the distribution of two classes (changed and unchanged) could be made more symmetrical.

Fig.1. Representation of the creation of difference images (I1 & I2 are input images).

The difference images are obtained by the Log ratio approach as D1 and by mean ratio approach as D2 considering I1 & I2 as input images and M1 & M2 as average filtered images by

$$D1 = |\log I1 - \log I2|$$

$$D2 = 1 - [\min (M1/M2, M2/M1)]$$

However, the information of changed regions that is obtained by the log-ratio image may not be able to reflect the real changed trends in the maximum extent because of the weakening in the areas of high-intensity pixels. The information of background obtained by the log-ratio image is relatively flat on account of the logarithmic transformation. Hence, it could be concluded from the above analysis that the new difference image fused by mean-ratio image and log-ratio image could acquire better information content than the individual difference images (i.e., the mean-ratio image and the log-ratio image).

B. NSCT Decomposition

NSCT decomposition is to compute the multi scale and different direction components of the discrete images. It involves two stages: Non Sub-sampled Pyramids (NSP) and Non Sub-sampled Directional Filter Banks (NSDFB) to extract the texture, contours and detailed coefficients.

Fig.2. NSCT Decomposition Flow.

NSP decomposes the image into low and high frequency subbands at each decomposition level and it produces $n+1$ sub images if decomposition level is n . NSDFB extracts the detailed coefficients from direction decomposition of high frequency subbands obtained from NSP. It generates m power of 2 direction sub images if number of stages be m .

C. K-Means Clustering

Clustering deals with finding a structure in a collection of unlabeled data. A cluster is therefore a collection of objects which are similar between them and are dissimilar to the objects belonging to other clusters. The steps for performing k-means clustering are as follows:

Step 1: Place K points into the space represented by the objects that are being clustered. These points represent initial group centroid.

Step 2: Assign each object to the group that has the closest centroid.

Step 3: When all objects have been assigned, recalculate the positions of the K centroid.

Step 4: Repeat Steps 2 and 3 until the centroid no longer moves.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Description of Data Sets

The input images are from a data set representing a section (301×301 pixels). Fig.3. shows the images acquired by a SAR sensor of the European Remote Sensing satellite over an area near the city of Bern, Switzerland, in April and May 1999, respectively. They are multi-temporal images, and as the name indicates, they are images acquired on the same geographical area, but at different times.

Fig.3. Mutitemporal images relating to the city of Bern used in the experiments (acquired in April 1999 and May 1999 respectively).

B. Results and Analysis

The difference images are obtained based on logarithmic ratio and mean ratio. The log ratio image enhances the low intensity pixels and weakens the high intensity pixels. In order to compensate this disadvantage, we use the log ratio image. The image obtained by fusing the mean-ratio image and log-ratio image could acquire better information content than the individual difference images (i.e., the mean-ratio image and the log-ratio image). The fused image thus obtained is highly robust to speckle noise.

Fig.4. Log ratio and Mean ratio images.

After the difference image creation, NSCT decomposition computes the multi scale and different direction components of the discrete images. The image fusion technique generates an image using the complementary information from the mean-ratio and log-ratio images. NSCT based fusion involves an average operator. And, maximum gradient coefficients are chosen to fuse the low-frequency and high-frequency bands to restrain the background information and enhance the information of the changed region in the fused difference image. A spatial fuzzy clustering algorithm is then implemented for classifying the changed region from the unchanged region in the fused image.

Fig.5. Fused image and the final change detected image.

C. Performance Evaluation

The performance of this method can be evaluated in terms of a few parameters such as Sensitivity (S), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) in order to make a comparison with the other change detection methods.

$$S = \frac{T_p}{T_p + F_n} \quad \text{MSE} = \frac{1}{M \cdot N} \sum_{i,j=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N (a_{ij} - b_{ij})^2$$

$$\text{PSNR} = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{255 \cdot 255}{\text{MSE}} \right)$$

where, a_{ij} is the pixel value at position (i,j) in the input image and b_{ij} is the pixel value at the same position in the output image. T_p and F_n represent the values of true positives and false negatives respectively. And, the square root estimation of the MSE gives the RMSE. In our method, the performance parameters thus calculated give the following values:

$$\text{Sensitivity} = 99.6127\% \quad \text{RMSE} = 0.0739$$

$$\text{PSNR} = 59.4422 \text{ dB}$$

The sensitivity or the value of correctness of this algorithm is estimated to be above 99.6% with relatively low errors.

CONCLUSION

Thus it is concluded that k-means clustering along with non-subsampled contourlet transform is an efficient method for change detection in SAR images with the help of complementary information from a log-ratio and mean-ratio image. Simulation results have also shown that this method is efficient in terms of performance parameters.

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